

Towards a Well-Educated Society in Tanzania: Exploring Socio-Economic Development at the Household Level

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ABSTRACT: This paper examines the status of household development influenced by education in Zanzibar, Tanzania. The study was conducted in the West District. A cross-sectional research design was used with a qualitative and quantitative approach. A sample of 120 was selected by simple random sampling procedures after treatment of area sampling by multistage sampling. Data collection methods involved a questionnaire survey, unstructured interviews, and a documentary review. Quantitatively collected data were analysed by descriptive statistics employing a statistical package for the social sciences to describe the variables of interest extensively. Qualitative data were analysed by theme and content analysis to capture the breadth of the topic. It was found that education had helped households to acquire food requirements, health services, and assets, and promoted livelihood due to income earnings. The participants were engaged in different employment activities, with the majority engaged in agricultural and small business activities. The study also revealed that parents' level of responsibility for educating children at the household level was high. The paper concludes that there was a high level of household education achievements, indicating purposive investments and adoption by local and national development actors in promoting access

to and outcomes of education enjoyed by households and community members. It was recommended that more efforts be made to enhance employment opportunities among youth through skillful and innovative educational skills at the basic level of education, namely primary and secondary education levels, that will promote self-employment to the youth who are the majority workforce in Tanzania. These could include investment in contextual and relevant skills of the agrarian, small business, blue economy, tourism, and rural economic activities of Tanzania.

Keywords: *A well-educated society, Children, Development, Household level, Zanzibar*

1. Introduction

Education is one of the most critical factors for any society's economic growth, social development, employment, and earnings (Woessmann, 2018). Van der Berg et al. (2018) argue that education significantly influences labour market outcomes. Education, mainly if it is of good quality, is a tool for development at the individual and society levels. This is due to its ability to equip individuals and society with the right skills needed to fully participate in the economy and society, particularly the labour market (World Bank, 2016; and Abdulahi, 2017). The quality of living among the majority of households is closely related to educational attainment. According to UNESCO (2018), in Papua New Guinea, people living in households headed by a person with no formal education constitute more than 50% of the poor. More significant equity in education enrolment and school quality across all population groups results in a more equal income distribution and reduces socio-economic inequalities in general (UNESCO, 2018). About 171 million people could be lifted out of poverty if all students in low-income nations left school with primary reading skills. This is equal to a 12% drop in the sum of the population that lives on less than United States Dollar 1.25 a day (UNESCO, 2018). The concept of household achievements in this paper encompasses the overall socioeconomic progress attributed to an individual's access to formal education and its influence on promoting access to and control of resources and livelihood promotion at the household level. It is a measure of the quality of life associated with the adoption of poverty reduction strategies and growth promotion at individual and household levels.

In 2000, world leaders announced the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in New York. One prominent goal in the education sector was universal primary education by 2015. Again, the other was to eradicate extreme poverty and hunger, reduce child mortality, and improve maternal health (UN, 2015). These goals were focused on the need to empower individuals and communities in knowledge, skills, and opportunities, starting at the household level, by development actors. Generally, interventions were done by every country to enhance access to education and the adoption of poverty reduction strategies. These efforts had evidence of promoting a high quality of life among societies. However, this required a localized analysis to understand how the strategies trickled down at individual and household levels in some specific societies. The education goal was regarded as one of the fundamental tools to stimulate the growth and empowerment of individuals. This requires a specific understanding of its achievement in various societies due to diversity and variations in practices among nations (UN, 2015). The current Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) agenda demonstrates the scale and prospect of the new Universal Agenda. The agenda focuses on ensuring inclusive and equitable education and enhancing lifelong learning opportunities for all as goal number four. The agenda imagines and ensures that by 2030, all girls and boys will compete for accessible, free, equitable, and quality primary and secondary education, leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes (UN, 2020). The SDG 2030 agenda on education further emphasizes that by 2030, all learners will acquire the knowledge and skills needed to promote sustainable development, including, among others, through education for sustainable development and sustainable lifestyles, human rights, gender equality, promotion of a culture of peace and nonviolence, global citizenship and appreciation of cultural diversity and culture's contribution to sustainable development (UN, 2020). Yet the extent to which education promotes the individual capacity to access and control resources at the nucleus of the community, namely, the household level, is still debatable insofar as poverty remains one of the great enemies of emancipation among community members in developing countries.

In developing countries, social researchers have accumulated evidence that education increases household productivity and thus increases the levels of income with many

non-monetary benefits out of education, such as improved health status, social control, and reduced crime (Lochner, 2018). Given the enormous global investment in education related to the implementation of the former MDGs that were adopted in 2000-2015 and the ongoing SDGs 2016-2030, statistics indicate that there has been a remarkable decline in the number of out-of-school children in developing nations from nearly 100 million in 2000 to 28 million in 2015 (UIS & UNICEF, 2019). This indicates the value of promoting a nation's human capital as an essential element for the achievement of household goals. This motivates developing nations to sustain the investment in the skills and human resources of their populations by widening and promoting the quality of education systems. According to UNESCO *et al.* (2018), there exists evidence of the positive developmental impacts of primary education, particularly for those working in agriculture, that have been generated over the past 40 years. A study that modelled the impact of attainment of education in fifty countries between 1960 and 2010 found that an additional year of schooling is likely to increase a person's earnings by 10% and the average Gross Domestic Product by 0.37% annually (Hanushek *et al.*, 2018). Another cross-country study showed that each additional year of education increases income by 10% (Metcalf *et al.*, 2019). In general, economic rates of return to individuals' and societies' investment in primary education were reported to be higher in low-income countries than in high-income countries and higher for primary education than for secondary or tertiary education (UNESCO, 2018). Muro and Burchi (2019), in examining the association between primary education and levels of food insecurity across 48 countries, indicated that doubling the attendance rates in primary education for rural populations would reduce levels of food insecurity by between 20% and 24%. Research that assessed the impact on income of the quality of education indicated higher than previously understood (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2017). According to UNESCO (2016), results in African countries indicated three distributaries by which education influences a household's productivity level. The first one is that it promotes the collective skills of the individuals to act in their roles quickly. The second distributary indicates that secondary and tertiary education levels adequately aid the transfer of knowledge about new information, products, and technologies innovated by others. Finally, education boosts households' capacity to innovate new knowledge, products, and

technologies by enhancing creativity. However, this evidence shows that education in developing African countries does not pull most household members out of poverty and improve their livelihoods despite increased access to and equality in education among household members. This now puts the continuous debate on the importance of education in general in promoting household members' socio-economic achievement. Again, the debate also lies in the thesis that increased years of schooling contribute positively to increased income among individuals. This is also challenging because of the evidence of low and non-immediate contributions of higher education at individual and household levels, which differentiates the currently developed from the developing countries' contributions of higher education.

Traditionally, the role of education in socio-economic development has been examined in the form of the linkage between education level and income, and in terms of returns, in which the existing indicator of social and individual rates of returns to investment in primary education was seen to have the highest, followed by the secondary education level. Return to higher education (HE) was observed to be the least (Bertrand et al., 2019). Although there were observed variances in the rates of return between several countries, it is usually indicated that investment in HE produces favourable rates of return at the individual level (19%) and society (10%) (Metcalf et al., 2019). Again, the key findings of eight African countries and universities in Botswana, Ghana, Kenya, Mauritius, Mozambique, South Africa, Tanzania, and Uganda concluded that there was a lack of clarity and agreement on a development model and the role of higher education in economic development, both at national and university levels (Clotfelter et al., 2018). Apart from that, HE, as opposed to basic education levels in developing countries, hosts a small minority of youth prepared for absorption in the socio-economic activities that create jobs.

In addition, the opportunities provided by universities in the eight countries also did not support knowledge production, and none of the countries had coordinated efforts between the government, external stakeholders, and universities to influence the contribution of the universities to development (Clotfelter et al., 2018). There was strong evidence that the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) literature only deals with comprehensive and complementary training that links to the labour market. Browne (2016) found that single-component TVET interventions

were not successful. Hanushek et al. (2017) concluded that the impact of vocational education varies considerably with the specific institutional structure of schooling and work-based training. However, the balance of early gains against later losses for vocational relative to general education is not uniform across these countries (Browne, 2016). Generally, Hemelt et al. (2019) state that increasing the level of education of the emerging workforce in developing economies will not ensure the easy absorption of higher-skilled labour into non-vulnerable jobs. This can be associated with the limited opportunities and slowness of growth of the private sector, connected to limited public employment opportunities in these countries. However, it is evident that the act of pushing forth the less educated, less-skilled young people into the labour market is a no-win condition, for both the youth who remain restricted to the hand-to-mouth livelihoods depending on unsustainable employment and for the economy, which receives a low level of contribution to enhancing the potential productivity. Normally, incomes increase depending on the employees' education level, and workers with higher education levels and/or more working experience can dream of acquiring more income. Returns to education vary significantly between employees in the paid jobs, under which an increase in education and additional years of education normally causes higher earnings, and those in own-account work, for whom big returns are far less certain.

Belghith and De Boisseson (2017) indicate that at the heart of the many problems faced by Sub-Saharan Africa are the intertwined challenges of rapid population growth and low human capital, which are concluded here as people with a particular education and health status. The human drivers of development comprise this linkage of population, education, and health triad in every region. However, in Africa, relationships are important in bringing people out of poverty. Levy (2018) argued that the link between education and poverty can be seen in two ways: firstly, investing in education as a tool to alleviate poverty can improve the skills and productivity of poor households, and secondly, poverty can be a barrier to educational attainment both at micro (children receive less education from poor homes) and macro (generally, poor countries do have lower enrolment rates) levels. According to Njong (2019), using the Cameroon Household Survey (CHS) conducted in 2001, education has an inverse relationship with an individual's poverty

status. This indicates that education is an important indicator of poverty. For instance, it was found that poverty is less prevalent among populations where the head of household has acquired a higher education level. Again, apartheid was found to create the opposite view in the level of poverty and wealth distribution and earnings among various communities. It was also found that ever since the practice of democracy, there had been no changes in South Africa and Limpopo Province. The majority of research on poverty in South Africa has shown a higher experience of poverty, particularly for the African (Black) population, than other racial groups (Belghith & De Boisseson, 2017). This can be linked, among other factors, to the lower level of educational attainment among black communities in this nation compared to other non-black communities.

According to the URT (2019), the Tanzania Development Vision (TDV) 2025 was envisioned to have a nation whose communities are imbued with a common developmental thinking and competitive spirit. These qualities are influenced by education that provides innovative thinking, skills, and knowledge. They are crucial in facilitating the country to adopt effective utilization of knowledge in an attempt to mobilise the local resources to ensure that their ability to realize the primary requirements and attainment of competitive advantages in the regional and global economy. According to this vision, Tanzania was expected to have attained creativity, innovativeness, and a high level of educational quality to be in a position to resolve the challenges of development and to have effective competition at the regional and international levels. The TDV 2025 further viewed that the citizens have an optimistic vision and a human development culture that promotes hard work, professional development, entrepreneurial skills, creativity, innovativeness, and ingenuity, and have confidence in and high respect for everyone, irrespective of gender. Lastly, it was expected to have a national education quality at all levels to be able to produce the quantitatively and qualitatively educated individuals that are sufficient and equipped with the requisite knowledge to resolve society's challenges (URT, 2019). This vision has localised implications in practices that require specific scrutiny to uncover the current progress.

2. Statement of the Problem

The former Zanzibar Development Vision 2020 ended with the achievement of universal education in 2019, with increased quality and number of local higher education institutions, with a high number of female students, over 50%, with increased quality of life from 48 to 65, and an increase in life expectancy in 2000 and 2012, respectively. Nevertheless, the ongoing Zanzibar Development Vision 2050 pillar two is oriented towards social and human development. It aims at enabling society to have quality health, competitive, innovative, and productive human capital that is aided by reliable, long-term, beneficial services for all populations. It aims to contribute effectively to national and global development (RGoZ, 2020). The Tanzania Development Vision 2025 aimed to realise a well-educated society by 2025 (URT,2019). Because of these development frameworks, programs and services to enhance education practices are vivid in Tanzania and the study area. Yet with all these efforts done, there was a need to understand how these development frameworks are realised at the household level. Most past researchers on education and achievements at the household level in Zanzibar have not examined the influence of education at the household level on economic and social welfare. That is, if real, the higher an individual's level of education, the more likely he/she is to achieve household-level socio-economic status (Armstrong et al., 2018; Botha, 2019). Given the achievements at the household level and the incessant focus on the significance of education, the past researchers had not effectively attempted to explore the achievements of the TDV 2025 policy framework in the area of education, namely, the envisioned well-educated society by 2025, and its achievements at the household level in Mjini Magharibi. Apart from Botha (2019), who has analysed the impact of education on poverty to a certain extent in Zanzibar, other studies have not tested this area of focus. That being the case, this research aimed to contribute new knowledge from where the past researchers left off. Therefore, this research explored the household-level achievements towards a well-educated society in the study area. Children and young people with parents who have lower educational attainment are less likely to do well at school than their peers with better-educated parents (White, 2019). Zanzibar is now on the brink of an enhanced increase in access to secondary and higher education, which is expected to lead to improved education quality for all

levels. According to the URT (2019), there is an increasing number of students who complete their primary education, and the demand for higher education is similarly increasing. These required the understanding of their outcomes and impacts at the household level.

2.1 Objectives

- i. To examine the status of the education of the children of households in the study area.
- ii. To examine the socio-economic achievements among household members in the study area.

3. Theoretical Underpinning

This paper employs the Power Cube Model to inform how educational power influences socio-economic participation and household achievements among household members in the study area. From the perspective of the Institute of Development Studies (2009), power appears in three aspects: these are levels, spaces, and forms. The power cube framework stresses that various levels (or layers) of relationship do appear vertically, involving the global (supra-national), national, and local levels. The spaces of power illustrate the three potentials for a or arenas for linkage: closed, invited, and claimed spaces. The power cube dimensions of power include the visible, invisible, and hidden power dimensions. The power cube framework proposes that invited spaces give room for participation and consultation, normally via the invitations done by different authorities, like the government, supranational agencies, or civil society organisations. It holds that the closed spaces include the decisions made by a set of actors that are behind closed doors, with no pretence of widening the boundaries for inclusion. The closed spaces, institutions, customs, laws, and the like impact people's lives but are considered off-limits for public involvement.

With regard to the framework, the claimed spaces for involvement are those spaces that the slightly powerless or excluded communities create for their own sake. These are the creations of the goodwill of others. The claimed spaces vary, from those formulated by social movements and community associations to those simply including natural places where people gather to debate, discuss and resist outside of

the institutionalized policy arenas. The visible forms of power are contests over interests visible in public spaces or formal decision-making bodies. Normally, these refer to political bodies, like the legislatures, local government authorities, local assemblies, or consultative forums. The hidden forms of power are those vested interests (persons or institutions) that formulate hindrances to involvement and retain their impact by influencing who gets to the decision-making table and who gets on the agenda. These variations operate at many levels to exclude and devalue the concerns and representation of the less powerful groups (Gaventa, 2005). The conception of invisible power explains how power is internalised, that is, the psychological and ideological borders of involvement, involving the practice (by dominant groups) of ideologies, values, and forms of behaviour, as well as various forms of behaviour by relatively powerless communities.

This framework links to the influence of education on socio-economic achievement due to the levels of power that education manifests among individuals at the household, community, organisation, national, and international levels. The education level determines the power levels and influence at various levels and, therefore, the ability to achieve socio-economically among individuals. Education is practised in various spaces of power. These include closed spaces, namely permanent employment by household members in various public, private, and not-for-profit entities. Another space is the invited spaces among household members, namely contractual activities, daily wage labour, part-time employment, and short-term seminars and training. The third claimed spaces include individual household member self-employment, working in community groups, volunteer non-governmental organisations, social networks, and social support groups. These spaces enable household members to participate, achieve socio-economic livelihoods, earn income, and acquire properties. The forms of power of education include visible educational power. This form involves educated household members, who form part of the legal organisations of decision-making at various levels. These include government bodies at various levels of policy-making and execution, private entities, non-profit organisations, and social groups. The other is the hidden power that involves barriers created for less educated household members, prohibiting them

from accessing opportunities at various levels and spaces, like access to formal employment and credits.

4. Methodology

The article is the output of the study conducted in Zanzibar, specifically in the Magharibi district. The selection of Magharibi was based on the fact that Zanzibar currently focuses on implementing the SDGs 2030 agenda on education, and the Tanzania Development Vision 2025. These long-term policy frameworks comprise the component of the education vision by 2025, namely, to realise a well-educated society by 2025. Hence, there was a need to explore the status of realisation at the household level by 2025. Moreover, Zanzibar Development Vision 2050 also emphasises inclusive and equitable quality education and promotes lifelong learning opportunities for all. This study employed a cross-sectional design to analyse the influence of education at the household level. This aided the understanding of the current status of educational influence on socio-economic achievement due to education at the household level in the study area. The researchers employed a mixed methods approach because of the need to describe the achievements at the household level in breadth and depth. The sampling unit was the head of household; selecting the head of household helped to obtain social and economic achievements resulting from educating members of households. A multi-stage sampling method was employed to choose the study area. West District was stratified with its administrative divisions, where two divisions were selected. Then, four Shehia, namely Mwanakwerekwe, Fuoni Kibondeni, Shakani, and Kombeni, were selected in the divisions. The third stage involved preparing the list of all villages in the selected Shehias; three villages were chosen purposely because of their dense population. The selection of the 120 respondents was done using simple random sampling methods after the formulaic calculation of the sample. The data collection methods involved a questionnaire survey. This employed a questionnaire to gather data from respondents. The documentary review method was also used to revise various documents and reports available in the study area. An unstructured interview was also a method that employed an interview guide to gather the data. The analysis of quantitative data involved data coding for easy entry using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences by descriptive statistical methods. Data

collected from the field were recorded, tabulated, computed, and described, edited, and split into simple parts; facts were consistently gathered, uniformly grouped, and put into the tables to obtain percentages for interpretation to determine the inherent facts depending on the type of complementary information. The qualitatively collected data from the documentary review and unstructured interview were analysed by theme and content analysis.

5. Results and Discussion

This part presents the characteristics of the sampled respondents. It presents and discusses the results of the study on the children's education status in the study area. It ends with the presentation and discussion of the socio-economic achievements of households in the study area, influenced by the education of household members.

5.1 Status of Education and Occupation at Household Level

This sub-section presents and discusses the results of the article. It presents and discusses the occupational results of the participants of the study. It also presents and discusses the results of the level of education held by participants of the study, as presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Participants' Characteristics (N = 120)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Occupation	Teachers	13	10.8
	Crop and animal husbandry	37	30.8
	Small Businessperson	23	19.2
	Health professionals	10	8.3
	Motorcycle-driver	11	9.2
	Drivers	7	5.8
	Fisherpersons	14	11.7
	Planning officers	2	1.7
	Students	3	2.5
Education	Non-formal Education	06	5.0
	Adult Education	00	00.0
	Standard Seven	5	4.2
	Form Four	36	30.0
	Form Six	24	20.0
	Above Secondary	49	40.8

5.1.1 Occupation

Table 1 shows that agriculture and animal husbandry are the primary occupations in the study area. About 37 (30.8%) of sampled respondents were engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry, and 23 (19.2%) were engaged in businesses. In comparison, 13 (10.8%), 14 (11.7%), and 2 (2.5%) of respondents were civil servants as teachers, doctors, and planning officers, and only 11 (9.2%) were employed in the informal sector. From these occupational statistics, it is evident that more than 90.8% of respondents were self-employed either in business, agriculture, or fishing (except civil servants), and it was also noted that farming in the area is done seasonally and probably affects the flow of income, especially before harvesting, when farming activities get intense. According to UNESCO *et al.* (2018), evidence of the positive developmental influence of primary education, particularly in agriculture, has been generated over the past 40 years. These results concur with the Power Cube Model that articulates various spaces for household members' participation in socio-economic activities. The most practical space in the study area is farming (crops and animals). This indicates the influence of claimed spaces for individual participation in agriculture among the majority of household members and less predominance of hidden powers in restricting individuals in these spaces as opposed to other closed and invited spaces requiring employment qualifications and procedures.

5.1.2 Education

Table 1 shows that 5 (4.2%) respondents were standard seven leavers, 36 (30.0%) were form four leavers, 24 (20.0%) were form six leavers, and 49 (40.8%) were above secondary school leavers. The data shows that many respondents were more educated with the above secondary education status. The fact that these results show a low illiteracy rate is apparent. Though several studies have suggested that education is a significant factor in determining success, knowledge increases one's rationality. This status indicates that there has been more inclusion of youth in education above the secondary level. According to the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar (2017), the learning outcomes of primary students appeared to have a gradual decline, whereby 20 per cent of students joining secondary education failed the Standard 7 performance, indicating significant unpreparedness for the next stage

of education. Again, it is indicated that the gap between the Form 4 examination pass rate and the percentage of students who meet the grade required to proceed to Form four is very large. This indicates that most students leaving school without proceeding to the next level of education have poor educational skills. This requires examining how they apply education to earning a livelihood at the household level. According to the United Nations (2020), all girls and boys should complete free, equitable, quality primary and secondary education, leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes (UN, 2020). However, these achievements require realisation at the household level among family members. The results indicate the participation of household members in education by the majority above secondary education, indicating the increased availability of spaces in education access.

5.1.3 Education Status of Children in the Household

For the purpose of scrutinising the linkage between education, societal levels, and household status, the researchers asked respondents to indicate the level of education of people in the household; the results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Children's Education Status in the Study Area (N=120)

i. Primary Level of Education

Figure 1 shows that 60 (50%) of respondents have children with a primary level of education. The results imply that households were benefiting from the level of education, even though they were benefiting in a minimal way, as described by some

of the heads of household in the study area. This is even more the case for socially and economically marginalised groups who have the most to gain from basic education. According to the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar (2020), education deprivation has been decreasing in Zanzibar, particularly in Magharibi “A” and “B”, indicating a 14% decrease in 2020 in the two districts from 19% in 2010. This indicates increased access to education at the basic level in the area.

ii. Secondary Level of Education

Figure 1 further demonstrates that 46 (38.3%) of respondents have children with a secondary level of education. The outcomes imply that households benefited from the education level described by some of the heads of households in the study area. These results align with those by UIS and UNICEF (2019), illuminating the ongoing Sustainable Development Goals 2016-2030 contribution to a remarkable decline in the number of out-of-school children in developing nations, from nearly 100 million in 2000 to 28 million in 2015.

iii. Higher Education Level

Figure 1 demonstrates that 14 (12%) of respondents have children with higher levels of education. The results indicate that educational level and household status are strongly related because some heads of household in the study area describe benefiting from the education level. However, the present statistics estimate on socio and individual rates of gains on investing in primary level of education indicate the highest gains, followed by the secondary education level returns; whereas the higher level of education ranks the least.

According to the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar (2017), enhancing human development to realise the expected progress objectives will need an important investment in resources in education to foster basic learning outcomes and to give cognitive and socio-emotional skills that are required for the acquisition of technical know-how in post-primary education. According to the 2022 Human Capital Index, a child born in Tanzania is 39 % of their productivity potential when educated with total health. Zanzibar holds an 18-year-old with 7.8 average schooling years. Despite this, the regulated average years of schooling are 5.1 years, showing an average loss

of 2.7 schooling years. The Zanzibar Development Vision 2050 is calling for quality, inclusive education and training programs to enhance learning outcomes. The plan stresses the necessity of acquiring the basic literacy and numeracy skills in primary and higher-order skills, including critical thinking, creativity, and innovation, and labour market-oriented skills development for the secondary level and beyond. This indicates the gap in the current primary and higher education practices that need redressing to enhance individual and household members' socio-economic achievements.

5.2 Socio-economic Achievements among Household Members

5.2.1 Education Achievements of Household Members

The paper examined whether education has helped households get food requirements, health services, peace and security, earn a high income, and account for the relationship between an educated society (in levels) and household status. In general, all respondents 120 (100%) agreed that educational achievement has a high contribution to the living standard of people. In order to explain the level of educational achievement among household members in the study area, the researcher developed a Likert scale; the results were explained as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Educational Achievements at the Household Level

Scale	Index Value	Frequency (%)	Weight	Weighted Mean
Education has helped households to meet their food requirements				
Strongly disagree	1	0 (0)	0	4.48
Disagree	2	0 (0)	0	
Neutral	3	0 (0)	0	
Agree	4	63 (52.5)	252	
Strongly agree	5	57 (47.5)	285	
Total		120 (100)	537	

Education has helped households to access health services				
Strongly disagree	1	0 (0%)	0	4.67
Disagree	2	0 (0)	0	
Neutral	3	0 (0)	0	
Agree	4	40 (33.3)	160	
Strongly agree	5	80 (67.3)	400	
Total		120 (100)	560	
Education has helped household to earn high income and properties				
Strongly disagree	1	0 (0)	0	4.50
Disagree	2	0 (0)	0	
Neutral	3	10 (8.4)	30	
Agree	4	40 (33.3)	160	
Strongly agree	5	70 (58.3)	350	
Total		120 (100)	540	

5.2.2 Education Achievement on Food Requirements

Table 2 shows that education has helped households meet food requirements; thus, 63 (4.48) of respondents agreed, while only 57 (4.48) strongly agreed. The results imply that education has helped households sustain their lives with food requirements. The results were similar to those of de Muro and Burchi (2019), who concluded that there is a strong relationship between education and food insecurity, whereby doubling the attendance rates in education for populations would reduce food insecurity by between 20% and 24%. The results relate to the Power Cube model's contention that there are levels and spaces of participation where household

members indicate an individual level of access to food at household spaces in the study area.

5.2.3 Education Achievement in Health Services Access

Table 2 shows that education has helped households get health services; consequently, 80 (4.67) respondents strongly agreed, whereas only 40 (4.67) agreed. The results imply that education has helped households sustain themselves in getting health services. The study related to the conclusion made by UNESCO (2016) reports that completion of basic education is associated with higher quality health indicators, progress on the other more by the completion of secondary education, for example, in sub-Saharan Africa, an estimated 1.8 million children's lives could have been saved in 2008 if the household had at least education a 41% reduction. According to the Power Cube Model, access to health services is mandated by visible forms of power, including those at local, district, regional, and national levels in Zanzibar. Therefore, the participation of household members has limited legal barriers, indicating a very high level of achievement.

5.2.4 Education Achievement on Income Earning

Table 2 above shows that education has helped households earn a high income in property, whereby 70 (4.50) respondents strongly agreed, 40 (4.50) respondents agreed, and only 10 (4.50) respondents were neutral. The results consider the amount of evidence on the positive income effects in education, especially for those working in productive sectors, as shown by respondents in the study. The results are similar to the views of Hanushek et al. (2018), who reported that an additional year of schooling can increase a person's earnings by 10% and average GDP by 0.37% annually. Generally, economic rates of return to individuals' and societies' investment in education have been reported to be higher in low-income countries than in high-income countries and higher for education (UNESCO, 2018). According to the Power Cube Model, income and poverty reduction strategies require space for household members' participation. The results imply that most individuals in households can earn income due to the invited, claimed, and closed spaces of employment that they possess in the study area.

5.2.5 Household Assets and Properties

Figure 2 presents results on the influence of education on household asset acquisition. It was found that households were able to acquire various assets linked to education outcomes, including vehicles, motorcycles, houses, and land.

Figure 2: Properties Owned by Respondents (N=120) Multiple Responses

Figure 2 shows that household assets owned by respondents included houses, which were evidenced by 87 (72.5%), while 11 (9.2%) of respondents owned land, bicycles, and cars, evidenced by 20 (16.7%) and 2 (1.7%) of respondents, respectively. The results imply that most households benefit from education by owning assets, perhaps because most households own houses and land. These assets have fewer economic multiplier effects than tangible and producible assets. However, the results provide theoretically important outcomes, such as household assets determining savings in the study area. Furthermore, households possessing durable goods had a significant effect on household status. The results indicate relevance to a cross-country study that proved evidence of the experience of educational benefits with an additional number of years of education at the individual level, leading to increased income by 10% (Metcalf et al., 2019). This income is helpful in an individual's ability to get access to quality of life, resources, assets, and property ownership.

According to the Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar (2020b), the deprivation of housing by residence remains widespread in Zanzibar's housing dimension of welfare in both urban and rural locations. However, the same enhancement levels were observed for children in rural and urban areas between 2010 and 2020, with a decrease in relative terms of 15% and 23%, respectively.

5.2.6 Household Members' Education and Their Achievements

Figure 3 presents results on the influence of education on household achievements. These achievements include socio-economic achievements like social status, properties, and living standards.

Figure 3: Educational Achievements at the Household Level (N=120)

Figure 3 shows that education has influenced acquiring properties by 112 (94.9%), getting married by 64 (54.2%), acquiring status in society by 112 (94.9%), and improving living standards by 112 (94.9%). The results imply that educational achievement has a strong relationship with socioeconomic status. However, it is evident that continuously pushing forward non-educated, non-skilled youth into employment opportunities is a no-win situation, both for the young people who are still destined for a hand-to-mouth livelihood based on non-sustainable work and for the economy, which gains little in promoting job potential. The returns to education vary greatly between employees in the paid jobs, for whom an increased number of years of schooling in general yields higher earnings, and those in own-account work, for whom significant incomes are far less certain, linked to educational attainment and socio-economic status. According to Lochner (2018), there are many argued experiences of non-monetary benefits of education, including improved health status, social control, and reduced crime. According to the Revolutionary Government of

Zanzibar (2017), there has been a continuous lowering in the people living below the poverty line. Again, there is an enhancement of the non-monetary indicators of poverty, like school enrollment and electricity access. The total housing deprivation for Magharibi “A” and Magharibi “B” Districts was 49%, indicating an increase due to population growth from 64% in 2010 (Revolutionary Government of Zanzibar, 2020b). This indicates limited education roles in promoting creation and innovation among family members to cater to the ever-growing population.

According to key informant interviews, most households in the study area possess educational knowledge. They have rural and urban experiences of livelihoods. Most families have integrated livelihoods; among them, they have skills acquired through the education system. These help them acquire formal employment. It was indicated that most family and household members are engaged in livelihood activities that were not part of the education system. These form a significant portion of family members with activities like fishery, carpentry, masonry, driving, small business, and cookery. One of the common responses among interviewees indicated the existence of two models of livelihoods among household members in the study, with education providing opportunities for formal employability and informal livelihood promotion activities that are not directly linked to one’s access to education, as argued by one respondent:

“It is surprising to see that what is learnt in schools and colleges is too formal and does not

apply to the particular situation of the learners' living environment. For example, one who learns at the primary, secondary, and even college level cannot use that education in his/her home environment in farming, fishing, or other related activities unless he/she is formally employed”
(Elderly Household Member, 2022)”.

The results imply that most household members in the study area, though educated at various levels, have adopted a multi-livelihood model of living that goes beyond formal knowledge and skills acquired through education. This indicates the challenging direct linkage of education to directly influence household members'

livelihood. This is also an alarm to redesign the educational contents at different levels to focus on the context and livelihoods of the graduates to equate the system of education to the lived experiences of life among graduates at various levels of education. The results are also linked to the Power Cube Model of participation that underscores the essence of claimed spaces and invisible power relations that concern the household members who are less educated, less skilled, and therefore have barriers that prohibit them from accessing visible claimed spaces and closed power for formal employment that could enable them to access plenty of socio-economic resources and opportunities for development.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

Generally, the researchers explored the achievements at the household level toward a well-educated society in the study area. The study reveals that household members possess diverse livelihood activities, with the majority engaged in crop and animal husbandry (37, 30.8%), followed by businesspersons 23, 19.2%). It was found that the majority of household members were educated above secondary education 49, 40.8%), followed by the secondary level of education (36, 30%). The evident achievements of the study area include enabling access to health services (with a mean of 4.67), being the highest achievement, followed by the enabled acquisition of high income and properties among members (with a mean of 4.5), and enhanced food requirements capacity (with 4.5 mean). It was found that the children's education status indicated that most children in the households of the study area had a primary level of education (50%), followed by a secondary level of education (38%). Higher education accounts for 12% of all children in the study area. The household members indicated evidence of acquisition of properties, with 72% of the respondents owning houses, followed by 17% owning bicycles, and 9% land resources. It was therefore concluded that the household members in the study area were actively promoting education strategies towards a well-educated society in Tanzania that contributes to influencing socio-economic outcomes of education at various levels by household members in the study area. This was shown through responsibility for educating children, ownership of properties and assets, and livelihood promotion through socio-economic activities, including agriculture, civil service employment, and

business endeavours that are outcomes of access to education. It was recommended that, in order to effectively achieve the strategy of a well-educated society that is dynamic to the changing world, efforts be invested in promoting skills-oriented and contextual basic education for most youth relevant to agriculture, micro and small businesses, tourists, and the blue economy society of Tanzania, areas that host the majority population with great investment potential. This is related to educational actors; agricultural, business, and fishery actors promote conducive spaces for effective participation in agriculture. Hence, there is a need to promote innovative incentives to attract citizens to the sectors, particularly the youth who hold the greatest workforce potential of the nation, through skillful education and training relevant to these subsectors.

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